

Synthetic and applied aspects of tin(IV) and organotin(IV) complexes of various Schiff bases

Raj Kumar Dubey* and Avadhesh Pratap Singh

Synthetic Inorganic and Metallo-organic Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : rajalkoxy@yahoo.com

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Abstract : The tin(IV) and organotin(IV) moiety form complexes with Schiff bases containing oxygen, nitrogen, sulphur or phosphorus coordinating atoms with varied coordination number. The development of new spectroscopic techniques FT-IR, multinuclear (^1H -, ^{13}C -, ^{119}Sn -) NMR, X-ray crystallography provided useful information about the structure. Recently, organotin(IV) complexes of Schiff base has extensively studied due to their antimicrobial, antineoplastic, anti-inflammatory, antitumour and antiurease activities. We reviewed the literature of tin(IV) and organotin(IV) complexes taking in to accounts on synthesis, spectroscopic characterization, biological importance as well as toxic behaviour of tin(IV) complexes of Schiff bases reported during recent years.

Keywords : Tin(IV), organotin(IV), Schiff base, multinuclear NMR.

Introduction

The study of coordination chemistry of tin has received much attention due to its ability to form complexes of various geometries and coordination numbers, known for both inorganic and organometallic complexes¹⁻⁹. It is well established in the literature that tin(IV) and organotin(IV) form more stable complexes with nitrogen, oxygen and sulphur containing Schiff bases¹⁰⁻¹⁹. Recently bioinorganic chemist attracted towards organotin(IV) complexes of Schiff bases, to couple therapeutic agents or systematically substituted molecules and different bio-molecules with organotin(IV) moieties in order to track variation and investigate their biological effect in biological systems²⁰⁻²³. However, important environmental problems have forced some nations to prohibit the use of such materials²⁴⁻²⁸. In spite of such drawbacks, organotin(IV) complexes among most widely used organometallic compounds as their potential applications^{29,30} such as their antiproliferative³¹, antitumour³¹⁻³⁴, antibacterial³⁵⁻³⁷, antifungal³⁸⁻⁴¹, antineoplastic^{42,43}, antiinflammatory^{44,45}, DNA cleavage⁴⁶⁻⁵¹ and cancer chemotherapy⁵² activities. The development in this field has been comprehensively reviewed⁵³⁻⁵⁵, reflecting the continued and enhancing interest in tin(IV) and organotin(IV)

complexes specially of ON; NS; ONO; and ONNO; bi-, tri-, and tetra-dentate Schiff bases. This present concern about the synthesis, characterization, biological applications, toxic behaviour as well as future aspects of tin(IV) and organotin(IV) complexes of Schiff bases.

Synthesis

Reactions of metal or organometal chlorides with appropriate Schiff bases salicylaldehydes (LH) :

Studies on molecular addition complexes of SnCl_4 were initiated during 1965-1967 by Russian workers⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸, who described large number of 1 : 2 adducts of formulation $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{RC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}=\text{NR}'$:

where R = H, 2-OMe; R' = Ph. R = 2-OH; R' = Ph, 4-MePh, 3-O₂NC₆H₄, 4-O₂C₆H₄⁵⁶. R = H; R' = Ph, 4-Me₂NC₆H₄⁵⁷. R = 4-Me₂N, R' = Ph⁵⁸.

Since 1967 interest in molecular adducts of tin(IV) and organotin(IV) with Schiff base ligands aroused considerable interest, which led to the preparation of different types of complexes in very large numbers. Account of such complexes has already been presented in three com-

prehensive review articles⁵³⁻⁵⁵. Furthermore, during the past 10-15 years, there has been renewed interest in molecular addition complexes; a brief description of their preparation is illustrated by following equations :

$n = 2; m = 2; R = \text{Me, Ph};$

$n = 2; m = 2; R = \text{Ph};$

$X = \text{OCH}_3, \text{Cl} \quad \text{solvent} = \text{EtOH}^{59}$

$n = 2; m = 1, 2; R = \text{Me, Ph};$

$X = \text{H, H, H, OCH}_3, \text{OCH}_3$

$Y = \text{H, 3-CH}_3, 4\text{-CH}_3, \text{H, CH}_3$

$\text{solvent} = \text{Et}_2\text{O}^{60}$

$n = 2; m = 1; R = \text{Me, Ph, } n\text{-Bu};$

$X = 2\text{-OH, 2-OH, 2-OH, 2-OH and 3-OCH}_3$

$Y = \text{H, 3-CH}_3, 4\text{-CH}_3, \text{H}$

$LH^{61-64} =$

Al-Allaf and Al-Shamas⁶⁵ reported the synthesis of some triphenyltin(IV) complexes :

$X = \text{OH, Cl, N}_3, \text{NO}_2; LH = \text{Structure of Schiff base ligand}$

$X = 2\text{-OH, 2-OH, 2-OH, 2-OH and 3-OCH}_3$

$Y = \text{H, 3-CH}_3, 4\text{-CH}_3, \text{H}$

$LH =$

Singh *et al.* have recently synthesized⁶⁶ a number of complexes with general formula R_2SnCl_2L/Bu_3SnClL by reaction of R_2SnCl_2/Bu_3SnCl with Schiff base derived from the condensation of 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde with thiosemicarbazide/semicarbazide hydrochloride in 1 : 1 molar ratio. Organotin(IV) adducts have been synthesized according to the following equation :

$R = \text{Me, Bu};$

L1

L2

The binuclear adducts formation between R_2SnCl_2 as acceptor and nickel(II) complexes of tetradentate Schiff base ligand as donor have also been reported^{67,68} shown as in equation :

$n = 1; M = \text{Ni}; X = 0;$

$R = \text{Me, } n\text{-Bu}; X = \text{H,}$

$3\text{-OMe, 4-OMe, 5-OMe,}$

5-Cl, 5-Br

$R = \text{Me, } n\text{-Bu, Ph};$

$X = \text{H, 3-OMe,}$

4-OMe, 5-OMeL

Further, binuclear adduct complex formation between R_2SnCl_2 as acceptor and M(II) complexes of tetradentate Schiff base ligand [ML] as donor have also been reported^{69,70} as shown in above equation :

$n = 1 \text{ for Cu, Ni, Co};$

$n = 2 \text{ for Fe, Mn};$

$R = \text{Me}^{69}$

$n = 1; A = \text{-(CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{)-,}$

$\text{-(CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{)-, } o\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-};$

$B = \text{H, Me}; C = \text{OMe, H,}$

$\text{Cl}; R = \text{Me, } n\text{-Bu, Ph}^{70}$

Interestingly, reactions of Me_2SnCl_2 with difunctional tridentate Schiff bases under refluxing methanol afforded five coordinated dimethyltin(IV) complexes⁷¹ :

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Reactions of metal or organometal chlorides with sodium salts of Schiff bases :

Structurally interesting complexes have been prepared according to the following equations :

During recent years, structurally interesting complexes⁷⁶⁻⁸⁰ of tin(IV) have been prepared by the reactions of $\text{SnCl}_4/n\text{-Bu}_3\text{SnCl}/n\text{-Bu}_2\text{SnCl}_2$ with sodium salts of N-arylsalicylaldehyde Schiff bases in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios by Dubey *et al.* according to the following equations :

L' = 2-picoline⁸⁰, 3-picoline⁸⁰, isoquinoline⁸⁰, γ -picoline⁸², pyridine⁸², quinoline⁸²

X = CHO, COCH₃

Reactions of organometal chlorides with Schiff bases in presence of triethylamine :

It involves elimination of phenolic proton by the formation of Et₃N.HCl and formation of structurally significant complexes :

R = Me, Et, Ph, Bn; M = Sn; LH = 2-[9H-purin-6-ylimino]-phenol; n = 2⁸⁵

R⁸⁶ = Me, Et, Bu, Ph, Bz;

R = Me; LH₂ =

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solvent = MeOH⁸⁹

R = Ph, Me, Et, *n*-Bu, *t*-Bu;

R = Ph, Me; LH₂ =

R = -CH₂C₆H₅, -CH₃

solvent = MeOH⁹¹

R = Ph, Me, Bu;

R' = 2-pyridyl, 2-thenyl, 1-naphthyl

solvent = C₆H₆⁹²

R = Ph, Me, Et, *n*-Bu, *t*-Bu;

R = Ph, Me, *n*-Bu;

R¹ = H CH₃ Cl NO₂

R² = H H H H

solvent = C₄H₈O⁹⁵

R = Ph;

R = Ph, Me, Et, *t*-Bu;

R = Me, Bu, Ph, Cy, Bz, *o*-ClBz, *p*-ClBz, Ph;

Reactions of dibutyltin diisopropoxide with appropriate Schiff bases :

Reactions of organotin oxides with Schiff bases :

Reactions of organotin oxides with a wide variety of

Schiff bases refluxing in suitable solvents (C₆H₆, CH₃CN, MeOH, EtOH) result in the formation of organotin(IV) chelates :

R = *n*-Bu, Ph, CH₂Ph;

LH₂ =

4-ClC₆H₄CH₂;

solvent = C₆H₆¹⁰¹

R¹ = CH₃ H H H

R² = H Ph H Ph

R³ = Ph H CH₃ H

R⁴ = H H H Ph solvent = CH₃CN¹⁰²

R¹ = H, C₆H₅, CH(CH₃)CH₂CH₃, CH₃, CH₂CH(CH₃)₂, CH(CH₃)₂, CH₂CH₂SCH₃, CH₂OH, CH(OH)CH₃, CH₂CH₂C₆H₅,

solvent = CH₃CN¹⁰³

R = Me, Ph;

R¹ = H, CH₃

solvent = EtOH¹⁰⁴

R¹ = H NO₂ H Me H C(CH₃)₂

R² = H H NO₂ H Me H

solvent = EtOH¹⁰⁵

R¹ = CH₂CH(CH₃)₂, C₆H₅, CH(CH₃)CH₂CH₃, CH₂CH₂SCH₃, C₆H₅CH₂

solvent = MeOH¹⁰⁶

R = Me, *n*-Bu, *n*-C₈H₁₇, Ph;

R¹ = H, OCH₃, NO₂

solvent = MeOH¹⁰⁷

In addition to the aforementioned examples, the synthesis of new class of bis-diorganotin(IV) compound reported by Beltron and co-workers¹⁰⁸ is shown in Scheme 1.

Properties

General physical properties :

The Schiff base complexes are colored (yellow, brown, orange, reddish orange, green red) solids, semisolids, viscous liquids or oily liquids, exhibiting molecular association depending upon (i) composition of the product, (ii) coordinating (bi-, tri-, or tetra-dentate) nature of Schiff

Scheme 1

base ligands, and (iii) nature of organic group attached to azomethine nitrogen atom.

Spectroscopic properties :

Characterization of Schiff base metal complexes were carried out by UV-Vis^{71,73}, IR^{56-74,76-80,82-108}, ¹H NMR^{56-65,71-108}, ¹³C NMR^{59-65,72,74-80,82-87,89,90,92-98,100-108}, ¹¹⁹Sn NMR^{59-66,71,72,74-80,84,85-88,90-98,100-108}, ¹¹⁹Sn Mössbauer^{85,86} and mass spectral^{71,76-80,82,83,89,90,98-100,102,105-107} studies. The disappearance of a band due to OH stretching frequency in the region 3885–2350 cm⁻¹ is consistent with the metallation of the phenolic proton, i.e. formation of metal-oxygen bond. The decrease or increase in ν_{C=N}, ν_{C-O} and appearance of new bands assignable to metal-nitrogen in the region 529–416 cm⁻¹ and metal-oxygen bonds in the region 654–500 cm⁻¹ were considered to be due to chelating behaviour of Schiff bases. These observations were further supported by ¹H NMR^{56-65,71-108}, ¹³C NMR^{59-65,72,74-80,82-87,89,90,92-98,100-108}, and ¹¹⁹Sn NMR^{59-66,71,72,74-80,84,85-88,90-98,100-108} spectral studies. ¹¹⁹Sn NMR^{59-66,71,72,74-80,84,85-88,90-98,100-108} spectral studies were found to be more useful in deciding coordination environment around tin metal centre.

X-Ray structures :

At present many examples of structural determinations of metal Schiff base complexes, to elucidate the general configuration of the molecule are available in literature^{71,74,75,81,84,87,89,90,93,94,96-98,100-108}. Therefore X-ray crystallographically determined structures of a few typical compounds are shown in Figs. 1–3.

Applications

Tin(IV) complexes play an essential role in agriculture, pharmaceutical and industrial chemistry. Ligands, the Sn moiety surrounded by a molecule, are used for the synthesis of complexes called as Schiff bases. Schiff bases with their tin(IV) derivatives are used as antimicrobial, antitumor, anti-inflammatory, anti-leishmanial, antiurease, DNA binding, cytotoxic, anti-liferative, and asphaltene dispersion inhibition activities. Some complexes also show optical and catalytic activities.

Fig. 1. X-Ray structure of bis[*N*-(3-*tert*-butylsalicylidene)-2,3,4,5,6-pentafluoroanilinato]dimethyltin(IV)⁷⁵.

Fig. 2. X-Ray structure of *N,N*-bis(3,5-dichlorosalicylidene)-1,2-phenylenediminetin(IV)dichloride⁸¹.

Fig. 3. X-Ray structure of dimethyltin(IV) [*N'*-(3-methoxy-2-oxidobenzylidene)-*N*-(oxidomethylene)hydrazine]⁹⁷.

Antimicrobial activity :

Organotin(IV) complexes of various Schiff bases (derived from condensation of salicylaldehyde with 2-aminopyridine, *o*-toluidine, *p*-toluidine⁷⁶; 2- or 3-aminopyridine with 2-hydroxy-, 2-methoxy- or 2-hydroxy-3-methoxy-benzaldehyde⁶¹; salicylaldehyde and adenine⁸⁶; pyridoxal hydrochloride with substituted hydrazide-isonicotinoylhydrazone, 2-thiophene carboxyl hydrozone⁹²; pyridoxal hydrochloride with 2-aminophenol, 2-amino-4-methylphenol, 2-amino-4-chlorophenol, 2-amino-4-nitrophenol, 1-amino-2-naphthol hydrochloride⁹⁵; 3-hydroxy-2-aminopyridine with 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-5-bromobenzaldehyde⁹⁶, 2-[9*H*-purin-6-ylimino]phenol⁸¹, *N'*-(2-hydroxybenzylidene)formohydrazide⁹⁰; *N'*-(5-bromo-2-oxidobenzylidene)-*N*-(oxidomethylene)hydrazine⁹³; *N'*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)formohydrazide⁹⁷; and bis-di-organotin(IV) complexes derived by one step reaction of 2 mole of leucine and Bu₂SnO/Ph₂SnO and one mole of 5,5'-methylenebisalicylaldehyde¹⁰⁸; and general formula of complexes [Me₂Sn(2-OArCH=N)C₅H₃NO] derived from 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine and substituted salicylaldehydes⁸⁹ (where Ar = -C₆H₃(5-CH₃), -C₆H₃(5-NO₂), C₆H₂(3,5-Cl₂)-, C₆H₂(3,5-I₂) showed remarkable activity towards bacterial species e.g. *Staphylococcus aureus*^{61,76,85,86,90,89,92,93,95-97}, *Bacillus subtilis*^{61,85,86,90,92,93,95-97,108}, *Pseudomonas vulgaris*⁶¹, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*⁶¹, *Pseudomonas*

aeruginosa^{61,76,85,86,89,90,93,96,97}, *Salmonella typhimurium*⁶¹, *Streptococcus flexneri*⁶¹, *Escherichia coli*^{76,85,86,89,90,92,93,95-97}, *Salmonella typhi*^{85,86,90,93,97}, *Eternobacter cloacae*⁸⁹, *Serratia marcescens*⁸⁹, *Enterococcus faecalis*⁸⁹, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*^{76,89}, *Shigella flexneri*^{90,93,97}, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*¹⁰⁸, and fungal species e.g. *Aspergillus niger*^{76,85,89,91,95}, *Aspergillus fumigatus*⁸⁹, *Aspergillus flavus*^{85,90,93,97}, *Candida albicans*^{76,90,92,93,95,97}, *Microsporium canis*^{90,93,97}, *Fusarium solani*^{89,93}, *Trichophyton longifusus*^{90,93,97}, *Candida glabrata*^{93,97}, *Fusarium oxysporum*⁸⁵.

Antitumour activity :

Series of new organotin(IV) complexes⁷³ of types R₂SnL, R=Me, Ph, *o*-Cl-C₆H₄CH₂, [R₃SnL]_∞; R = *n*-Bu (H₂L=2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde-5-chloro-2-hydroxybenzoyl hydrazone) have been found to exhibit good *in vitro* tumor activity towards lung cancer cells (A549), human colon cancer cells (HCT-8) and promyelocytic leukemia leukemic cell line (HL-60). *n*-Butylsubstituted tin(IV) complex exhibit greater activity than methyl, phenyl and *o*-chloro benzyl substituted tin(IV) moiety. Diorganotin(IV) complexes of the type bis(2-[9*H*-purin-6-ylimino]pheno-late Me₂|Et₂|Bu₂|Ph₂|Bz₂-Sn(IV) have been screened against human cell line KB, which derives from a human oral epidermoid carcinoma by using DMSO to solubilize the complexes prior to use in biological experiments⁸⁵. All these complexes were found to have certain inhibitory effect, but diethyl-tin(IV) complex showed the most promising cytotoxic effect against the cell line which is even better than the *cis*-platin under the same experimental condition⁸⁵, whereas, triorganotin(IV) complexes⁸⁶ of the type R₃SnL (where R=Me, Et, *n*-Bu, Ph, Bz; L = anion of Schiff base derived from salicylaldehyde and adenine) assed for cytostatic activity against the human cell line KB and all complexes show significant cytostatic activity, whereas tributyltin(IV) complex is more active than *cis*-platin. Recently Lec *et al.* studied⁹⁸ anticancer activity of diorganotin(IV) complexes of the type R₂SnL [H₂L = (*E*)-*N'*-[5-bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl)ethylidene]-3-hydroxy-2-naphtholhydrazide and (*E*)-*N'*-[1-(5-chloro-2-hydroxy-phenyl)ethylidene]-3-hydroxy-2-naphthohydrazide; R = Me, Bu, Ph, Cy, Bz, *o*-ClBz and F-ClBz against three human carcinoma cell lines HT-29, SKOV-3 and MCF-7. These ligands were

found to display good cytotoxic activities towards all the cell lines with IC₅₀ below 8 µg/ml. The IC₅₀ value of dimethyltin(IV) derivative of (*E*)-*N'*-[5-bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl]ethylidene]-3-hydroxy-2-naphthohydrozide even better than the cytotoxicity of *cis*-platin. The cytotoxic activities decrease as follows : dibutyltin > decyclohexyltin > dibenzyltin > di(*p*-chlorobenzyltin)tin > di(*o*-chlorobenzyltin)tin > diphenyltin derivatives. The diphenyltin derivative displays selectivity against HT-29 cells whereas, di(*o*-chlorobenzyltin)tin and di(*p*-chlorobenzyltin)tin against MCF-7 and SKOV-3 cells. (*E*)-*N'*-[1-(5-Chloro-2-hydroxy-phenyl)ethylene]-3-hydroxyl-2-naphthohydrazide derivative of dicyclohexyltin show good cytotoxic activities in all the tested cell lines with IC₅₀ values below 1 µg/ml. The di(*p*-chlorobenzyltin)tin derivative of this ligand displays selectivity against MCF-7 cells. Diorganotin(IV) compounds¹⁰⁵ of multicomponent reaction of α-amino acid (isoleucine, leucine, methionine and aminopenyl acetic acid), 2,4-dihydroxy benzaldehyde, 2-hydroxyl-4-methoxybenzaldehyde, and *n*-Bu₂SnO/Ph₂SnO were tested in tumoral cell lines cervical uterine adenocarcinoma (Hela), colon adenocarcinoma (HCT-15) and breast adenocarcinoma (MCF-7) and results exhibit high activity in all cell line.

Anti-inflammatory activity :

The anti-inflammatory activity of five novel organotin(IV) complexes of the type R₃SnL (where, R = Me, Et, *n*-Bu, Ph, Bz; L = deprotonated Schiff base derived from salicylaldehyde and adenine) have been screened and the results obtained indicate the order of anti-inflammatory activity⁸⁶ of R₃SnL complexes as follows : *n*-Ph₃SnL > *n*-Bz₃SnL > Bu₃SnL > Et₃SnL. The present anti-inflammatory value was calculated as

$$\text{Percent anti-inflammatory value} = \left(\frac{1 - \text{DT}}{\text{DC}} \right) \times 100$$

(where DT and DC are the volumes of paw edema drug treated and control group, respectively).

Anti-leishmanial activity :

The anti-leishmanial activity of six new diorganotin(IV) complexes⁹⁰ of *N'*-(2-hydroxybenzylidene)formohydrazide (H₂L) with general formula R₂SnL, where R = Ph, Me, Bu, Oct, *t*-Bu, Et, and L = [OC₆H₄CHNNCHO] and ligand, were obtained against the pathogenic leishmania

major using Amphotericin B and Pentamidine as standard drugs. These complexes showed a significant reduction in viable promastigotes. Ethyl derivative show highest potential as leishmanicidal agent with IC₅₀ 0.90 µg/ml. Recently Shujah *et al.* describe the anti-leishmanial activity⁹⁷ of *N'*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)formohydrazide ligand and its dimethyl, diethyl, diphenyl, di-*n*-octyl, di-*tert*-butyl and *n*-butylchlorotin(IV) derivatives against the pathogenic leishmania major using Amphotericin as standard drug. All the organotin(IV) complexes showing more activity than the corresponding ligand which is due to the vital role of Sn atom. The *tert*-butyltin(IV) and diphenyltin(IV) complexes showed comparative activity than standard drug due to their higher lipophilic character⁹⁷.

Asphaltene dispersants/inhibitors :

New class of bis-di-organotin(IV) complex synthesized by a one step reaction of two molecular equivalents of leucine, *n*-Bu₂SnO or Ph₂SnO and one of 5,5'-methylene-bissalicylaldehyde have tested for asphaltene dispersants/inhibitor¹⁰⁸, by determining the asphaltene concentration in solution after precipitation with *n*-heptane using UV-Vis spectroscopy technique for two compounds and found that *n*-butyl derivative is more effective than phenyl derivative. The efficiency was defined as the ratio of absorbance of the test samples over the reference.

$$\% \text{eff} = \frac{A_{\text{exp}}}{A_{\text{ref}}} \times 100$$

(where A_{exp} is the absorbance of the test sample supernatant and A_{ref} is the absorbance of the reference sample).

Antiurease activity :

Recently Ali *et al.* describe *in vitro* anti urease activity⁹⁷ of *N'*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)formohydrazide ligand and its dimethyl, diethyl, diphenyl, di-*n*-octyl, di-*tert*-butyl, *n*-butyl chlorotin(IV) derivatives, using thiourea as the standard inhibitor having an IC₅₀ I.S.D. [µM] value of 21 ± 0.01 and found that the parent ligand and its organotin(IV) derivatives are moderate urease inhibitor except dimethyltin(IV) derivative which show excellent activity with IC₅₀ ± S.D. [µM] value of 101 ± 2.16. This is due to its ability to establish secondary interaction with the active site of enzyme.

Toxic effect :

The rapid progress in biological, industrial and biological applications of tin(IV) complexes during the last few decades has led to their accumulation in the environment and in biological systems. Organotin(IV) compounds are characterized by the presence of at least one carbon tin(IV)-carbon bond. The organotin(IV) compounds classified as mono-, di-, tri-, and tetra-organotin(IV) as depending on the number of alkyl or aryl moieties. Most organotin(IV) compounds are generally very toxic, even at low concentration. The biological activity is essentially determined by the number and nature of the Schiff bases/organic groups attach to tin atom. It seems that the nature of anionic group is of only secondary importance. The trialkyltin(IV) and triaryltin(IV) complexes powerful toxic action on central nervous system. In the series of $R_3Sn(IV)$, $Me_3Sn(IV)$, and $Et_3Sn(IV)$ are the most toxic when administered orally, and toxicity decreases as we move from tri-*n*-propyl to tri-*n*-octyl, the later not being toxic. However, tributyltin(IV) complex to be used as biocide agent in antifouling paints for ships. However, important environmental problems have forced some countries to ban the use of such materials.

Conclusions

Tin(IV) and organotin(IV) complexes of various Schiff bases are synthesized by different synthetic routes; reactions of metal or organometal chlorides with appropriate Schiff bases, sodium salts of Schiff bases, with Schiff bases in presence of triethylamine, reaction of metal or organometal alkoxide with appropriate Schiff bases, reactions of organotin oxides with Schiff bases, among these more facile and commonly employed methods of their synthesis are sodium salt, in presence of triethylamine and removal of water method. The new spectroscopic techniques FT-IR, multinuclear (1H -, ^{13}C -, ^{119}Sn -) NMR, X-ray crystallography are successfully used to distinguish the variety of structural features of these complexes. Recently, some organotin(IV)-Schiff bases exhibit very good antimicrobial, anticancer, anti-inflammatory and antiurease activities. However, the action mechanisms of the organotin-Schiff base complexes are not well known or

not well studied, so new techniques need to be applied to understand how the organotin-Schiff base complexes exert their biological activity. However, tributyltin(IV) complex to be used as biocide agent in antifouling paints for ships. However, important environmental problems have forced some countries to ban the use of such materials. Since there is no substitute yet discovered, therefore, work on organotin(IV) still continued due to scope of their use.

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